

Optimizing Retrieval in Libraries through RAG: A Framework

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Abstract

This research study shows through demonstration that it is quite possible to develop a low-cost question-answer-based search system for libraries by using open source tools and open source large language models (LLMs). The typical problems associated with LLMs are hallucinations and out-of-date, non-contextual answer generation. Surprisingly, it has been found that the same LLMs can generate better contextualized answers when augmented with a set of relevant documents. This process of augmenting relevant documents in LLMs before the generation of answers is known as retrieval-augmented generation. This research study deployed an array of open source tools in a RAG pipeline and used open source LLMs deployed through Ollama and Groq to demonstrate the power of RAG systems in developing conversational search systems for libraries. The study concluded with a set of possible applications of RAG-based systems in libraries in the near future.

Keywords: Retrieval Augmented Generation; Large Language Models; Generative AI; ChatGPT; Gemini; LlamaIndex; LangChain; Llama3

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1. Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) exhibit impressive capabilities in generating human-like text but also encounter challenges like hallucination and non-contextual responses (Agrawal et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2023). RAG, or Retrieval Augmented Generation, is a technique in natural language processing that enhances LLMs by combining retrieval-driven and generation-based approaches, enabling them to access external knowledge sources for more accurate, coherent, and contextually relevant outputs, akin to a librarian retrieving information from a vast collection of books to provide comprehensive answers. There are four major techniques for improving the performance of an LLM (Figure-0), while Prompt Engineering offers ease of use and flexibility, RAG and Fine-Tuning generally achieve higher accuracy on specialized tasks but require more resources and expertise (Ovadia et al., 2023). Pre-training from scratch is the most complex method but allows for complete customization. The choice among these methods should be based on the specific requirements of the LLM application, balancing accuracy, flexibility, and resource investment (Lewis et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2020).

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Figure 0. Improvement techniques for LLMs (source: <https://lnkd.in/dt3m2ycT>)

All these methods have their strengths and weaknesses, but RAG's ability to maintain context, deliver factual responses, and provide richer information at a low computing cost and minimum technical expertise makes it a compelling choice for conversational search systems in libraries. It offers a user-friendly and adaptable solution that empowers libraries to enhance search experiences and connect users with the information they need in a more natural and engaging way.

2. Large Language Model

The genesis of Large Language Models (LLMs) can be traced back in two parts – neural network based machine learning backend and transformer architecture:

- Neural Networks and Language Processing (1950s onward): Early research on neural networks in the 1950s laid the groundwork for machines to process language. This involved experiments by IBM and Georgetown University researchers (Guu et al., 2020).
- Transformer Architecture and Self-Supervised Learning (2017 onward): The concept of LLMs really came about in 2017 with Google's Transformer model. This neural network architecture excelled at finding patterns in vast amounts of text data. This coincided with the rise of self-supervised learning, where models learn from unlabeled text, allowing them to become more general-purpose (Devlin et al., 2018).

2.1. What is a Large Language Model

A Large Language Model (LLM) is a sophisticated artificial intelligence system with a vast parameter count that excels in natural language processing tasks, understanding, and generating human-like text based on extensive training data (Prince et al., 2023). These models, powered by transformer architectures, can weigh the importance of words in a sequence, capturing relationships to produce contextually relevant text. LLMs are available both from commercial and open access domain (Lan et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2019):

GPT-4 by OpenAI:

- Description: The fourth generation of the Generative Pre-trained Transformer models, known for its advanced capabilities in natural language understanding and generation.
- Applications: Used in applications like ChatGPT, offering conversational AI services.
- Access: Commercial

BERT by Google:

- Description: Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers, a transformer-based model designed to understand the context of a word in search queries.
- Applications: Enhances Google Search by improving the understanding of search queries.
- Access: Commercial

Llama 2 and Llama3 by Meta (formerly Facebook AI)

- Description: Llama 2/3 is the successor to the original Llama model, developed by Meta AI. It builds upon the architecture of its predecessor with improvements in training methodologies, data preprocessing, and model scaling.
- Applications: Used in diverse fields, from academia to industry, for developing advanced AI applications.
- Access: Open Access Mistral
- Unlike commercial LLM providers who keep their models veiled in secrecy, Mistral's core LLM, Mistral 7B, is freely available for download. This allows researchers and developers to tinker with the model, understand its inner workings, and even tailor it for specific purposes

2.2. Problems of Large Language Models

Large Language Models (LLMs) have indeed revolutionized natural language processing with their remarkable capacity to generate human-like text across a wide range of topics and questions. However, alongside their impressive capabilities, they also present several significant challenges that need to be addressed:

- Hallucination: LLMs can sometimes generate text that is not grounded in reality or facts, leading to inaccuracies or misinformation. This hallucination can occur when the model generates content that sounds plausible but lacks factual accuracy (Ji et al., 2023).

- Out-of-date data: LLMs trained on vast amounts of text data may inadvertently incorporate outdated or incorrect information into their responses. This can lead to the dissemination of obsolete or inaccurate knowledge (Lewis et al., 2021).
- Generic answers: Due to the nature of their training data, LLMs may produce generic or cliched responses that lack depth or specificity. This can result in uninformative or unhelpful answers to complex questions (Tonmoy et al., 2024).
- Non-contextual responses: LLMs may struggle to maintain context across longer passages of text, leading to responses that are disjointed or irrelevant to the input. This can hinder the model's ability to generate coherent and meaningful text (Shuster et al., 2021).
- Ethical concerns: The use of LLMs raises ethical considerations regarding the responsible deployment of AI technology, including issues related to bias, privacy, and the potential misuse of generated content (Fan et al., 2023).

For example, a query to Gemini (an AI-based conversation search system from Google) to know the reactions of the global leaders after the successful completion of the project Chandrayaan-3 by ISRO, India, has produced no answers due to its lack of knowledge about this project (Figure 1). Addressing these challenges requires ongoing research and development efforts to enhance the accuracy, reliability, and ethical implications of LLMs. By mitigating these issues, LLMs can continue to advance the field of natural language processing while ensuring the responsible and beneficial use of AI technology.

Gemini ▾

Figure 1. Gemini's response against a valid query on Chandrayaan-3

3. Plausible Solution

The problems of LLMs as discussed in section 2 generally handled by experts deploying two improvements techniques, namely, Fine-tuning and RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation). These are techniques designed to mitigate limitations in large language models (LLMs).

Regarding hallucination and out-of-date data, fine-tuning exposes the LLM to a focused dataset on a specific domain, ideally containing accurate and current information (Roberts et al., 2020). This retraining process helps the LLM learn patterns and relationships within that domain, reducing the influence of inaccurate or outdated information from its broader training data. On the other hand, RAG retrieves relevant information from a curated, up-to-date knowledge base during the generation process, ensuring the LLM's responses are grounded in factual and current data, thus preventing reliance on potentially outdated internal knowledge. In addressing generic answers, fine-tuning uses focused training data to expose the LLM to domain-specific language and concepts, enabling it to generate more specific and relevant responses (Ovadia et al., 2023). RAG enhances specificity by retrieving information that directly addresses the user's query, providing the LLM with a specific context and factual details, resulting in more informative and focused answers. To tackle non-contextual responses, fine-tuning on longer texts improves the LLM's ability to maintain context by learning how different parts of a text relate to each other. This leads to more cohesive and consistent responses. Similarly, RAG enhances context awareness by leveraging retrieved information relevant to the entire user query, ensuring that the LLM's responses are more aligned with the overall conversation flow (Lewis et al., 2021). It is important to note that the effectiveness of both fine-tuning and RAG depends on the quality of the data they utilize. Fine-tuning relies on accurate and domain-specific training data, while RAG's success depends on the comprehensiveness and currency of the knowledge base. Table 1 shows a comparison between these two techniques.

Table 1: Fine-tuning vrs. RAG

Feature	Fine-Tuning	Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)
Purpose	Adapts a large language model (LLM) for specific tasks	Integrates external knowledge sources with LLM for richer responses
Method	Trains the LLM on a smaller, task-specific dataset	Retrieves relevant information from a knowledge base and feeds it to the LLM for generation
Strengths	Improves performance on specific tasks	Provides more factual and contextually relevant outputs
Weaknesses	Limited to the knowledge encoded in the fine-tuning data	Can be slow for a CPU-based system as it is computationally expensive due to semantic search process
Suitability	Tasks requiring high accuracy on specific domains (e.g., legal document analysis)	Tasks requiring access to external information (e.g., question answering)
Cost	Higher (requires significant compute resources)	Lower (potentially lower compute cost for inference)
Infrastructure	More demanding (high-end hardware for training)	Requires access to and management of a knowledge base

In the context of a library, considering both cost and technical expertise, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) might be a better approach than fine-tuning for following reasons:

- **Cost:** RAG generally requires less upfront investment. While maintaining a knowledge base has its own costs, it's typically less expensive than acquiring the significant compute resources needed for fine-tuning large language models through retraining. Libraries often have existing resources like digital collections and databases that can be leveraged to build a knowledge base, further reducing costs (Wu et al., 2024).
- **Technical Expertise:** Fine-tuning LLMs can be complex and requires expertise in machine learning and large language models. Libraries may not have technical staff with this specific skill set. RAG, on the other hand, can be implemented with a more accessible knowledge base management system, potentially requiring less specialized technical knowledge.

Owing to these facts, this research study has explored a RAG pipeline to develop a question-answer-based interface for libraries by deploying open source tools and open access large language models (LLMs).

4. Workflow of a RAG Pipeline

RAG is a technique used to improve the responses of large language models (LLMs) by incorporating information from external sources. The work flow of a RAG pipeline involves the following steps (Alshammari et al., 2023; Bradley, 2023; Fitch, 2023):

- **Create a project:** A project workspace is established where the Large Language Model (LLM) can access embedded documents. Documents must be embedded within this workspace for the LLM to see or utilize their content.
- **Upload Document:** This process converts the documents (many formats are supported like pdf, word and warc to name a few) into plain text (called chunks), preparing it for embedding.
- **Embed Document:** This action divides the text into manageable chunks, which are then processed by the embedder model to generate numerical representations called vectors process is known as vectorization).
- **Store Vectors in Database:** This step is critical for the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) process, though it does not ensure that related text chunks remain together, a subject of ongoing research.
- **Submit Query:** Users type a question into the chatbox and submit it.

- **Embed Query:** The system embeds a question in the same way it did with the document text, transforming it into a vector representation.
- **Retrieve Relevant Chunks:** The vector search (also called semantic search) calculates the nearest document vectors to the given query vector using a mathematical process called Cosine Distance. The system filters out any low-score text chunks. Each vector retains the original text from which it was derived. This step is influenced by the embedder model and various settings in the selected RAG pipeline.
- **Prepare Context for LLM:** The valid text chunks are then passed to the LLM as the original text. This text (as context) is included in the LLM's "System message" component.
- **Generate Answer:** The LLM uses the system prompt, the provided context, user query, and the conversation history to generate the most accurate response possible with references to the source documents.

Figure 2 depicts a basic RAG pipeline explaining the workflow as discussed in the foregoing paragraph

Figure 2. A basic RAG workflow

(source: How I built a Simple Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Pipeline by Dr Julija Bainsksina)

5. Designing a Prototype

The primary objective of this research work is to develop a RAG-based question-answer system for libraries by deploying open source tools and open access LLMs in place of the costly API-based commercial services like OpenAI and Gemini (Table 2). Open-source RAG frameworks like LlamaIndex and LangChain empower libraries to build question-answer (Q & A) systems using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) with freely available large language models (LLMs) like Llama2, Mistral, and Orca. This approach offers significant advantages compared to costly commercial tools and models. First, it eliminates licensing fees, making it a budget-friendly option for organizations and individuals. Second, open-source tools promote transparency and foster collaboration, allowing developers to customize the system to their specific needs and contribute to its ongoing improvement (Wang et al., 2023). Additionally, the vast community surrounding open-source projects provides valuable support and resources. Finally, using open-source LLMs ensures access to the latest advancements in LLM research, keeping the question-answer system as developed at the forefront of capabilities. As a whole, open-source RAG pipelines offer a cost-effective, adaptable, and robust solution for building powerful facilities in libraries through Q & A systems. This research study has selected WarcGPT – an open source RAG systems based on LangChain as pipeline, developed by Harvard Law School Library and available under MIT license

Table 2: Components of the Prototype

SL	Role in the System	Name of Tool	Reason for Selection
1	Operating system	Ubuntu LTS 24.04	A stable Linux distro with huge user base
2	Programming environment	Python 3.12 (along with Poetry V. 1.8.3)	Most of the RAG systems are Python based applications
3	RAG pipeline	LangChain	As it is more comprehensive indexing and retrieval tool in comparison to LlamaIndex
4	RAG system	WarcGPT	It is based on LangChain and supports API-based access alongside Web UI
5	Vector store	ChormaDB	The default vector database and vector similarity search engine in the deployed RAG pipeline
6	Embedding tool	intfloat/e5-large-v2	Text Embedding model available through Hugging Face
7	LLM deployment	localOllama and Groq	Tools to run large language models locally with support for an array of open source LLMs

8	LLMs (Ollama) (Open Access)	llama2:latest mistral:7b-instruct mistral:latest orca-mini:latest orca2:latest	Users can select any of these models from Ollama library during Q & A sessions (Ollama library can be populated with any number of open source LLMs)
9	LLMs (Groq) (Open Access)	LLaMA3 8b LLaMA3 70b Mixtral 8x7b Gemma 7b	Groq is a mission oriented OpenAI-compatible GenAI inference, helping real-time AI applications
10	Web UI	Stramlit	A powerful tool for creating a web user interface (UI) for a RAG system

A Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) pipeline that utilizes Warc files for ingestion offers several advantages (in comparison to other file formats like pdf, doc, txt etc):

- **Scalability and Efficiency:** Warc files are designed for archiving large web crawls. They efficiently store massive amounts of text data in a compressed format. This allows the RAG pipeline to ingest and process significant datasets without requiring excessive storage space or processing power.
- **Preservation and Integrity:** Warc files maintain the original structure of the crawled web pages, including metadata like timestamps and URLs. This ensures the information retrieved by the RAG system retains its context and provenance. This can be crucial for tasks like historical analysis or legal applications where maintaining the original source is important.
- **Accessibility and Standardization:** Warc is a widely recognized and well-documented archive format. This makes it easier to find and share Warc datasets, promoting collaboration and re-usability within the research community. Additionally, the standardized structure of Warc files simplifies the ingestion process for the RAG pipeline, reducing development and maintenance efforts.
- **Flexibility and Adaptability:** Warc files can encompass various web content types, including text, HTML, images, and even multimedia. This flexibility allows the RAG pipeline to be adaptable and ingest information from diverse web sources. This can be particularly valuable when dealing with comprehensive knowledge bases that require information beyond just text.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Since Warc files are often compiled from publicly available web crawls, leveraging them can be a cost-effective way to build a knowledge base for your RAG system. This can be especially beneficial for organizations with limited budgets who cannot afford access to curated commercial knowledge bases.

- **Processing Complexity:** While Warc files offer many benefits, processing them can be computationally expensive compared to simpler text formats. This is because the RAG pipeline needs to extract relevant information from the web page structure within the Warc file.
- **Data Cleaning:** Warc files can contain duplicate content or irrelevant information from the web crawl. The RAG pipeline might require additional data cleaning steps to ensure the quality and accuracy of the ingested information.

In other words, a Warc format-based RAG pipeline offers a scalable, efficient, and cost-effective approach to building knowledge bases for question-answering systems. The ability to preserve context, manage diverse web content, and utilize readily available datasets makes it a compelling choice for various applications. However, it's important to consider the potential need for additional processing and data cleaning when working with Warc files (Hoshi et al., 2023; Yan et al., 2024).

6. Experiment and Methodology

The prototype based on WarcGPT is tested with a set of documents (converted to Warc format) on the Chandrayaan-3 project of ISRO, India accomplished in July-August, 2023. Next, the RAG pipeline ingests the Warc-formatted files before testing the prototype with a series of questions. This experiment evaluating a RAG-based question-answer system for a library setup involves the following steps:

6.1. Data Collection

This research study gathered a comprehensive set of newspaper articles, totaling 150 in number, from reputable online newspapers from all over the world. These articles were carefully selected to focus on reports related to the Chandrayaan-3 project, a significant space exploration endeavor. In addition to these news articles, the study also collected press releases from prominent space agencies such as the Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO), the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), and the European Space Agency (ESA). The collection period spanned from July 23rd, 2023, to September 30th, 2023, ensuring that the dataset captured a wide range of reports and updates on the Chandrayaan-3 project during this timeframe. After a thorough evaluation of the content, the study narrowed down the selection to 143 news items and press releases that were deemed most relevant and informative. The URLs of these selected news items were then stored in a text file, which served as input for generating a Warc file. This dataset on Chandrayaan-3 serves as a valuable example of how this methodology can be applied to other areas. For instance, libraries can extend this approach by collecting and analyzing documents related to their rules, facilities, services, and subscription bases. This can ultimately lead to the development of a question-

6.2. Warc Conversion

The benefits of utilizing the Warc format have been previously elucidated in Section 5 of this research report. Notably, the Warc format is capable of efficiently storing large volumes of text data in a compressed format, thereby optimizing storage capacity. Furthermore, generating Warc files from a list of websites (URLs) is a relatively straightforward process. In a Linux-based environment, this can be accomplished with ease using the 'wget' command (Table 3).

Table 3. Wget command and switches to produce warc file from a file of given URLs

wget	• --mirror enables mirroring to recursively download all files from the specified URL and its subdirectories.
--mirror	
--warc-file=	• --warc-file=psm_data sets the name of the WARC file to "psm_data".
--warc-max-size=	• --warc-max-size sets the maximum size of the WARC file.
--warc-cdx	• --warc-cdx generates a CDX index file alongside the WARC file.
--page-requisites	• --page-requisites downloads all necessary files for proper page display, such as images and stylesheets.
--html-extension	• --html-extension appends the .html extension to HTML files when saving them.
--execute robots=	• --execute robots=off ignores the robots.txt file to download all content without restrictions.
--directory-prefix=.	• --directory-prefix=. specifies the current directory as the location to save downloaded files.
--wait=	• --wait=1 adds a delay of 1 second between each page request.
--no-check-certificate	

6.3. Ingestion

The process of ingestion in this RAG system uses LangChain as RAG pipeline, ChromaDB as vector store, and intfloat/e5-large-v2 as embedding tool. The ingestion process begins with data collection, where raw text data is gathered from various sources. This data is then preprocessed, which involves tokenization, stopword removal, and stemming or lemmatization to normalize the text (Berant et al., 2013). The preprocessed text is then embedded into dense vectors using the intfloat/e5-large-v2 embedding tool, which converts the text into numerical representations that can be stored and queried efficiently (Lan et al., 2020). These embedded vectors are then stored in ChromaDB, a vector store that allows for fast similarity searches and efficient storage of vectors (semantic search). Once the vectors are stored, the LangChain RAG pipeline is used to generate a retrieval index, which enables the system to

quickly retrieve relevant documents based on semantic similarity (Yang et al., 2015). The retrieval index is then used to augment the generation capabilities of the system, allowing it to generate more accurate and informative responses to user queries (Figure 3).

The result window of the RAG system designed using Streamlit (tool to develop web UI in Python) shows how it takes a user query in natural languages, converts the query into vectors, matches with document vectors to retrieve top 4 relevant documents in the collection, and then augment the retrieved documents to the selected LLM to generate answer (Figure 4).

This chatbot can answer questions about web archive files it ingested.

Settings Inspect Stop Ask

Starting part of response from the RAG pipeline

Secondly, Russia's space program has faced significant challenges in recent years, including the failure of the 2011 Fobos-Grunt mission and the decline of its space legacy [4]. This may have impacted the development and execution of the Luna 25 mission.

Lastly, India's ISRO has demonstrated a strong track record in space exploration, with successful missions like Chandrayaan-1, which discovered water on the moon in 2009 [3].

In conclusion, the differing outcomes of the Luna 25 and Chandrayaan-3 missions can be attributed to factors such as mission timelines, program experience, and the challenges faced by Russia's space program.

References:

[1] Popular Mechanics - "Russia's Luna 25 Probe Crashed Into the Moon"
 [3] CNBC-TV18 - "Chandrayaan-3 vs Russia's Luna 25: Who is Likely to Win the Space Race?"
 [4] CBC News - "Russia's Luna 25 mission to the moon ends in failure"

End part of response from the RAG pipeline

Figure 4. Result in RAG system

This research study has also conducted a series of experiments involving the direct submission of questions to the LLM in use, Llama3-70b, without utilizing RAG, which means not augmenting retrieved documents. Then, the same questions were posed to the same LLM, Llama3-70b, but this time with RAG, which involves augmenting retrieved documents through semantic search. In every case, it was found that the LLM in use failed to provide accurate answers and, more alarmingly, produced confidently incorrect answers (a phenomenon known as hallucination) when not using RAG. However, in every such case, the LLM produced correct and informative answers by referring to sources when used with RAG (as illustrated in Figure 5).

Figure 5. No RAG vs. With RAG

The results of this study demonstrate the significant impact of incorporating the RAG system into the question-answering process. The experiments clearly show that LLMs are prone to producing confidently incorrect answers when not augmented with retrieved documents through semantic search. In contrast, when used in conjunction with RAG, LLMs consistently provide accurate and informative answers. These findings underscore the potential of the RAG system to improve the reliability and accuracy of large language models (Li et al., 2024; Siriwardhana et al., 2023), and suggest that this approach may be a valuable strategy for solving the problem of hallucination in AI-generated responses.

7. Conclusion

Open-source Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) unlocks a future of boundless information services by libraries. Libraries can deploy tools like LangChain, LlamaIndex, and open-source LLMs like Llama3, Mistral, and Groq to enhance search services in addition to the traditional keyword based search systems. The possible future applications may be represented under two main categories (Fitch, 2023; Gur et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022):

Patron Support:

- **Intelligent Chatbots:** RAG-powered chatbots can answer user queries with precision, drawing from internal and external knowledge sources.
- **Automated Cataloguing & Indexing:** Intellectual tasks like cataloguing and indexing can be streamlined, allowing librarians to focus on more patron-centric services.
- **Personalized Recommendations:** RAG can curate personalized book recommendations, ensuring patrons discover the most relevant materials for their needs.
- **Automated Metadata Generation:** Metadata creation can be automated, improving discoverability and searchability of library resources.
- **Interactive Exhibits & Displays:** Imagine dynamic exhibits powered by RAG, providing patrons with engaging information experiences.

Empowering Research & Learning:

- **Virtual Research Assistants:** RAG-powered assistants can guide patrons through research queries, suggesting relevant materials and fact-checking information.
- **Content Summarization:** RAG can generate summaries of books and articles, allowing patrons to quickly grasp key points and identify relevant resources.

This is just the beginning. Open-source RAG offers limitless possibilities for libraries to evolve into dynamic information services, catering to the diverse needs of their communities. The potential lies with librarians and information professionals to explore and harness this power, ultimately enhancing the user experience in library access.

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